

MEDICAL SCIENCES

REMOTE MEDICAL CONSULTATIONS FOR PATIENTS: PRO ET CONTRA

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ABSTRACT

The year 2020, marked by the pandemic, caused an explosive growth in demand for telemedicine services, especially remote consultations and patient monitoring. The author analyzed data from over 100 articles by Georgian and international authors, 117 reviews of internet resources, and laws related to the keywords „remote patient consultation“ and „pandemic.“ Several publications were selected for this work, and the author's own opinions and experiences are presented. Today, remote consultations in Georgia are used for initial visits, preventive appointments, referrals to clinics, and obtaining second opinions, with the possibility of prescribing additional tests. Over the past 20 years, there has been significant growth in the development of remote consultations, long-term health monitoring, and the use of mobile apps for tracking vital signs. An important aspect is the legal regulation of telemedicine use, but it remains imperfect and needs revision. The COVID-19 pandemic has driven the development of telemedicine technologies in the public health system.

Keywords: Remote patient consultations; remote patient monitoring; remote health monitoring; COVID-19 pandemic.

Problem Statement. The year 2020, marked by the pandemic, caused an explosive growth in demand for telemedicine services. Reducing the burden on healthcare systems through remote consultations and remote monitoring of health indicators has become not only desirable but also essential for both patients and the healthcare system as a whole. At the same time, this area of telemedicine, which is currently expanding, has been actively developing throughout the past decade. Remote consultations with patients have evolved alongside the spread and training of the population in the use of the Internet and various communication devices.

Analysis of the Latest Research and Publications. The author analyzed data from 169 articles, 117 analytical reviews of Internet resources, and laws related to the keywords “remote patient consultation,” “mobile applications for patients,” and “pandemic.” For this work, 38 publications were selected, and the author's own opinions and experiences are presented.

Identification of Unresolved Aspects of the Problem. Some aspects are subjective, as Internet resources—such as their pages and content—have been removed over time and cannot be cited.

Aim of the article. The paper aims to identify the positive and negative aspects of remote medical services, to reveal their ratio, and the prospects that remote medical services have.

Results.

Remote consultations on websites. Since 2000, there has been an active development of various Internet resources for conducting remote consultations with patients [1, p.2]. As a rule, they have a multi-clinic format - consultations of doctors of different specialties are conducted on one site. There are very few mono-specialized resources, and they are distinguished by their commitment to one medical institution (private clinics are leaders in this area), one doctor, personal

consultations to create the image of a group, or one specific specialist.

For consultative medical Internet resources in the period 2010-2020, the following were characteristic:

- Lack of general rules for consultations
- Possibility of diagnosis, prescription of treatment
- Unsystematic development - with an outpatient focus, doctors of not all specialties were present. As a rule, this was due to the level of implementation of Internet technologies in a particular specialty.
- Imperfection of the technical component of consultations - standard forums, chats were used, the inability to attach examination results, etc.
- Lack of protection of patients' data.
- Not all Internet resources required confirmation of the consultant's qualifications, and verification of the authenticity of the documents provided was complicated.
- Inflated expectations and adverse reactions from patients - patients hoped to completely replace an in-person visit to the doctor, including diagnosis and treatment, including prescription drugs, and, not receiving this, were left with a negative experience of receiving a remote consultation.
- On the part of doctors, a formal approach to conducting consultations, using templates for answers to the most common questions, and maximizing the conversion of an absentee appointment to an in-person one.
- In fact, the patient rarely received a quality medical consultation.
- However, gradually over 10-15 years, the main unspoken rules of remote consultations were formed:
 - Do not make a diagnosis, but express an assumption.
 - Do not prescribe prescription drugs.
 - Orient the patient to the initial examination and

in-person appointment.

- If the patient and the consultant live in the same place, conversion to an in-person appointment can be allowed.
- If possible, recommend a specialist from the patient's region of residence.
- Complete the consultation - if necessary, bring it to a logical conclusion
- Do not convince healthy people that they have a disease - in some cases, simply engage in educational activities.
- Do not consult patients under 18 years of age.

From 2009 to 2020, there was an "explosive" growth in demand for online consultation resources - each medical institution, each department, clinic, and doctor began to offer their platforms for remote consultations with patients.

The main problem remained the low clinical value of consultations and inflated expectations of patients.

For Georgia, 2021 was a turning point in many ways, when Law No. 2 "On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of Georgia on the Application of Information Technologies in the Sphere of Healthcare", commonly referred to as the "Law on Telemedicine", adopted on July 29, 2020, came into force. Today, TM is not prescribed in the legislation. [3,p.12]. At the same time, as several domestic experts in the field of healthcare organization emphasize, the elaboration of the regulatory framework in this area remains deeply insufficient. In particular, "all of the above documents did not create a legal basis for the activities of medical workers in remote examination or monitoring systems" [4, p.9]. On the one hand, the Law was heavily criticized by the professional community and the business industry; on the other hand, it contributed to the development of the sector.

New features of remote consultations over the past 10 years can be considered:

- The emergence of high-quality Internet information resources for patients, which include a section for patient consultations.
- Monetization - the emergence of official paid consultations, which made it possible to increase both the motivation of consulting doctors and their responsibility for the consultation.
- Changing the vector of remote consultation from patient lead generation (referral to a clinic) to the desire for a full-fledged medical consultation.
- The development and use of gadgets for monitoring various indicators of the body's condition have become a breakthrough technology in medicine, and their active use during the pandemic has become vital for many patients. Today, the wearable device market in 2019 amounted to almost \$27 billion and is likely to grow to \$64 billion by 2024 due to increased concern among people about their health during the COVID-19 pandemic, when they are seriously interested in tracking contacts with infected people, predicting symptoms, and monitoring health [5, p.41].
- Formation of a separate area - remote patient monitoring. In 2020, a search was conducted for publications on the use of remote patient monitoring in PubMed for the period 2010-2024. Data analysis showed a

steady increase in the number of studies on this topic, with 43% of them published between 2015 and 2018 and showing generally positive observational results (76.8%). Of these articles, 38.2% were published in the United States. The topic of almost half (47.8%) of the total number of studies was remote monitoring in cardiovascular diseases, and surgical pathology and post-operative care were considered in only 2.6% of publications. As expected, the most popular monitoring strategy was using wireless wearable devices and smartphone applications (75.7%). In addition, 17.6% of studies included elements of tele-education, and 24.6% - teleconsultations. The review authors concluded that remote monitoring combined with remote consultation maximises the effectiveness of treatment and patient care, and the growing number of publications demonstrates the high interest in the topic [6, p.8].

- Increased demand - a sharply increased need for consultations from patients. According to Sakstat, 2/3 of Georgian citizens know about the possibility of receiving medical care remotely - 25% of respondents are ready to see a doctor remotely - 53% of respondents are ready to accept an appointment by phone, residents of Tbilisi, Batumi (60%) and other large cities (56%) answered affirmatively more often. 48% of respondents intend to seek advice online, and the number of young people (18 to 24 years old) who accept online appointments is more than half, 57%. [7, p.9]. One study surveyed 301 general practitioners and 3,009 patients in the UK, Germany, and the Netherlands. The study was conducted in November 2020 and showed that the most preferred digital tools used by people over 55 are remote monitoring (50%) and video examination (50%) [10, p.21]. In the United States, the number of patients seeking remote medical consultations in the first quarter of 2020 increased by 50% compared to the same period in 2019, with most of the requests not related to COVID-19 [11, p.5]. According to a telephone survey by the State Statistics Service of Georgia, as of May 26, 2023, 62% of respondents knew about the possibility of receiving a remote medical consultation, and in Tbilisi, this figure was 71%. However, only 8% of respondents used telemedicine assistance [12, p.8].

- The emergence of remote medical service packages - one-time online consultations; unlimited online consultations for various periods of 1 month, 3 months; nursing care; urgent or scheduled consultations [13, p.9].

- Support for the possibility of providing remote medical care during the pandemic by the Ministry of Labor Protection and Health and its consolidation in the Order of October 30, 2020, No. 11.

- The problem in providing remote care to patients is the need to authorize all patients receiving telemedicine care. In this regard, the possibility of obtaining an anonymous consultation is excluded. Consultations in which the patient's data is not visible to the doctor are technically feasible; they will be hidden, but complete anonymity is excluded.

- Another problem from the doctor's side can be considered the need to consult strictly from an office that has a license for the profile of providing telemedicine care. This limits the possibilities of conducting a

consultation.

- Telemedicine consultations can only be provided by doctors registered in the register of medical workers and working in a medical organization [15, p.33].

- A critical milestone in the development of TM technologies was the appearance of telemedicine consultations and remote monitoring in the nomenclature of services. The decision on payment is made at the level of subjects by tariff commissions.

- Today, remote consultations in Georgia are used in the case of an initial consultation - a preventive appointment, referral to clinics, and obtaining a second medical opinion with the possibility of prescribing additional examinations. Because the Law strictly regulates the conduct of an initial consultation, doctors ignore the Law and covertly make a diagnosis and make appointments. In 2020, a special legal regime for testing new technologies was discussed in Georgia, within the framework of which it is possible to suspend specific legal provisions that impede the testing of these technologies [19, p.11]. Similar ways of introducing innovations are already working in Israel, Singapore, and the USA [20, p.45].

Remote medical care has shifted from simple teleconsultation to long-term remote monitoring, which looks extremely promising in terms of further development from discrete to continuous.

If, for example, earlier blood pressure measurements could only be taken at a doctor's appointment, a general urine test could be done. Only in a clinical laboratory can we see continuous receipt of information when measuring blood pressure at home using a portable tonometer or, for example, obtaining a general urine test using a portable urine analyzer connected via a smartphone to special medical services developing using cloud technologies [21-24].

We can note a noticeable increase in the number of available hardware solutions designed for individual monitoring of the functional indicators of the body - fitness trackers, single-channel ECG devices, portable analyzers, and even Holter monitoring [25, p.9].

An integral requirement for devices used for remote health monitoring is registration with the Ministry of Healthcare of Georgia as a medical device [26]. The peculiarities of regulating the issuance of permits in Georgia, a formal approach to the registration of medical devices, unfortunately, lead to the fact that the Georgian market is poorly represented by solutions that appear in large quantities on the international market—Telemedicine in state-owned health care institutions. Until 2010, the focus in state-owned health care institutions in consultations was on the doctor-to-doctor format; after 2010, the focus shifted to the doctor-to-patient format. The executive branch, the Ministry of Health of Georgia, supported doctor-to-doctor consultations. For example, since 2019, remote consultations of doctors in relevant areas have been carried out [27, p.33]. A register of medical institutions that can consult on these platforms has been created, typically consulting doctors from regional and state-owned healthcare institutions.

Standards and reporting indicators for remote consultations were developed and introduced in both state and regional health care institutions.

Several regions of Georgia have begun to implement their plans for the introduction of technologies for remote monitoring of population health indicators with the possibility of subsequent teleconsultation.

Participation of mobile operators in the development of telemedicine. The largest Georgian mobile operators are actively involved in the development of TM technologies, with their client base and mobile technologies. In 2020, one of the largest Georgian mobile operators, MAGTI, offered public and private medical institutions a project based on the Internet of Things to provide health monitoring services and telemedicine consultations. Medical devices equipped with the operator's SIM cards should automatically transfer data to cloud storage, where they will be aggregated in an anonymized form, so that only the attending physician will see the patient's data in the interface designed for this purpose. Just as in the previously described regional projects, the first solution for remote monitoring of health indicators of patients with hypertension was presented to medical institutions [31, p.60]. Another major telecom operator, Silknet, has proposed and is developing the 120/80 application, which is designed to monitor blood pressure with the ability to consult with a doctor, create your observation log, and a joint project of the AVERSI clinic network and the SmartMed telemedicine platform provides a range of digital healthcare products and services [32, 33, p.11].

TM consultations during COVID-19. It is evident that the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly limited face-to-face contact between people in all areas of activity, accelerated the development of remote monitoring and telemedicine technologies. Several authors claim that the healthcare sector as a whole has made a ten-year leap in just one year of fighting the pandemic [35, p.2]. For example, doctors from the digital medical service Doctor Nearby, part of the VEB Ventures portfolio, conducted 227.9 thousand consultations in 2020, which is 293% more than in the pre-crisis 2019. Revenue increased by 21% year-on-year, to \$684.4 million [36, p.17]. A research report commissioned by the non-profit organization Mobiquity says that half of patients over the age of 55 preferred digital tools over face-to-face consultations with a doctor during the pandemic [37, p.20]. On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared the COVID-19 pandemic, which put the healthcare systems of all countries without exception in harsh conditions and required several restructuring actions. First of all, the system of emergency and planned medical care for patients with COVID, as well as patients with chronic diseases, including cancer, without COVID, was subject to changes. The shortage of medical personnel, the repurposing of medical institutions, and a sharp increase in the number of patients led to a reduction in medical care for the population. This was a prerequisite for lifting several restrictions in the provision of telemedicine care to patients. At the beginning of the pandemic, on March 20, the establishment of state remote consulta-

tion centers for the treatment of COVID-19 and the regulations for its interaction with similar centers in all regions of Georgia were announced [38, p.22], as well as the Temporary Regulations for the organization and provision of advisory medical care using telemedicine technologies to citizens with a confirmed diagnosis of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19, as well as with signs or a confirmed diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia, acute respiratory viral infection, influenza, receiving medical care in an outpatient setting (at home). This document approved the procedure for providing remote advisory assistance to patients, including treatment adjustments, their logistics to medical institutions, if necessary, opening and closing sick leave certificates, and issuing electronic prescriptions. [38, p.18]. Undoubtedly, the emergence of these documents and their implementation in practice have become a giant step in the development of telemedicine consultations. It remains controversial to maintain this format after the end of the pandemic at the same volume.

Development of mobile applications for patients.

The development of remote medical consultations has led to an increase in the participatory nature - active involvement and personal participation of patients in the diagnostic and treatment process [30, p.6].

A significant milestone in the development of TM consultations was the emergence and growth of mobile applications for patients. A new study by Juniper Research has shown that the number of people using medical and health applications will grow from 627 million in 2020 to more than 1.4 billion in 2025 [31, p.7].

A report by J'son and partners consulting, published in 2024, also emphasized that the fastest growing segment of the mobile health market was smartphone applications, which, in turn, were proposed to be divided into four categories according to their primary tasks:

- tracking fitness and health indicators;
- medical information (directories, information, diagnostics, education);
- telemonitoring and remote consultations;
- healthcare management (electronic medical records, logistics, and payment support).

These categories can include mobile applications for:

- chronic patients
- medication control [32, p.10].
- women's health control.

According to the document, Georgia was not among the top 15 countries in the world at the time of its publication: specialists from the analytical company counted only 16 mobile healthcare projects, products or services presented in Georgia at that time, but even then we predicted a significant increase in activity in this area, especially for large cities [33, p.21].

However, in 2021, the Grand View Research forecast review already included Georgia in the TOP-50 countries showing the most excellent prospects in the field of telemonitoring of health indicators, teleconsultations, and mobile healthcare [38, p.34].

Data from various analytical sources regarding the size of the market for mobile telemonitoring applications already in 2013 varied significantly, with estimates ranging from \$2.4 to \$6.3 billion. The only unanimous forecast was regarding the growth trend in this area [5, p.18]. In 2018, this figure was estimated to be at least 8 billion. It is expected to exceed 111 billion dollars by 2025. Zion market research analysts note the high potential and demand for health monitoring technologies for people with diabetes, obesity, hypertension, and cancer. It is also stated that as of 2017, the United States accounted for about 40% of the market. Still, the Asia-Pacific region is expected to develop more and more noticeably and rapidly in this area, primarily due to the high population and significant burden of chronic diseases [35, p.5]. In 2020, the global market for mobile devices for health monitoring, diagnostic devices, and services is estimated at 23.1 billion dollars. However, in the coming years, it will grow rapidly and reach 250.5 billion dollars by 2027. At the same time, the average annual growth rate from 2020 to 2027 will be 40.6%. Moreover, for example, the figure for cardiac monitors is projected at 41.8% per year. In absolute terms, this segment will reach 46.1 billion dollars by 2027. And this is not the fastest-growing segment. Thus, sales of devices for people with diabetes will grow by an average of 46.9% per year [36, p.3].

The following aspects can be highlighted in the development of mobile applications for patients in 2010-2025:

- A sharp increase in the number of mobile applications over the past 15 years.
- Active participation of pharmaceutical companies and manufacturers of medical equipment in the development of the market of mobile applications for patients with various nosologies.
- Not consistently high technical and functional quality of mobile applications.
- The ability to log in in several ways, download files with examinations.
- Patient involvement in maintaining their health and the ability to prevent deterioration in health.
- Monetization of mobile applications,
- Almost all mobile applications do not have intrusive advertising.

Examples of the implementation of TM technologies. The most striking and complete example of the implementation of TM technologies in consulting is telemedicine pre-trip examinations of drivers, including measuring body temperature and blood pressure, measuring alcohol on exhalation, examining the skin, checking for fatigue, taking psychotropic drugs, and a general survey on well-being.

The positive aspects of this format are the absence of the human factor, strict regulation of parameters, and reduced time for examination. The disadvantage is the lack of a clear legislative framework on this issue. None of the documents regulate how exactly the medical examination should be carried out - remotely or in person, thereby creating legal uncertainty in this matter.

The need to develop specific algorithms for the remote examination format was emphasized, allowing, without violating the law, to remotely determine the

functional state and make a decision on whether to admit or not admit a driver or other employee to their functional duties. It should be noted that due to the restrictions that have arisen due to the spread of the new coronavirus infection, this proposal is becoming more relevant. In the coming years, remote consultations and remote monitoring will be actively developed and used in the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of patients. In almost all areas of medicine, some form of remote monitoring of patients is possible.

Conclusions and recommendations

TM has transformed from regular consultations to long-term (continuous) monitoring of health using medical devices, which can be considered one of the most promising new areas with clinical effectiveness. TM technologies are gradually becoming a familiar tool in clinical practice and can become routine for doctors and patients even after the end of the pandemic.

1. Remote technologies for monitoring and consulting patients have undergone significant development and transformation, and have become a driver for the development of medicine and a new perspective in clinical and economic decisions.

2. The current Law regulating the use of TM technologies, although it requires its development, has become a trigger for their widespread implementation in clinical practice. 3. TM has transformed from regular consultations to long-term (continuous) health monitoring using medical devices, which can be considered one of the most promising new areas with clinical effectiveness.

3. The COVID pandemic has become a driver for the development of TM technologies in the public health care system.

4. TM technologies are gradually becoming a familiar tool in clinical practice and can become routine for doctors.

5. Remote monitoring and consulting technologies using special hardware technologies and test systems have become a familiar and recognizable solution for many patients.

6. Patient and doctor loyalty to remote monitoring technologies will increase, and demand will grow. High expectations remain on both sides.

7. Further development and improvement of the legislative framework, as well as funding for telemedicine services, are necessary.

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